

Electrochem 2019

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CONTINUE

Submission ID

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Title

Corrosion study of magnesium alloys coated with chitosan coating in the Hank's solution for biomedical applications

Abstract

In recent years magnesium and its alloys became one of most promising materials to be used in biomedical applications. Because of its strength, toughness, elasticity modulus is very similar to the human bones. Moreover, it takes part in different important living processes in nature at all, and in humans body in particular. Magnesium shows very good biocompatible and biodegradable properties but on the other hand it is unstable in the solutions containing the chloride ions. To improve corrosion resistance of magnesium it was applied natural biopolymeric chitosan coating.

In this work, the corrosion rate of Mg₁₉Zn₁Ca alloy in the Hank's solution was investigated. In order to study the corrosion degradation of Mg alloys the following electrochemical techniques were used: Linear Sweep Voltammetry (LSV), Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), chronoamperometry. The corrosion tests were performed in the Hank's solution at 37°C and pH = 7.2. The microstructure of alloys has been investigated by means of XRD and FE-SEM/EDS measurements. Surface analysis techniques like XPS and FT-IR were used to study the chemical composition corrosion products.

Magnesium alloys undergo active corrosion in the Hank's solution. The chitosan based coatings deposited on the surface of Mg alloys significantly reduce their corrosion rate. Chitosan layer on the surface of Mg alloys produces a corrosion protective film and also shows antibacterial properties.

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Authors and Affiliations

Iryna Kozina (Presenting)

AGH - University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Foundry Engineering, Krakow, Poland

Maria Starowicz

AGH - University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Foundry Engineering, Krakow, Poland

Halina Krawiec

AGH – University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Foundry Engineering, Krakow, Poland

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